

International Peer Review Journal

p-ISSN 1817-5562

e-ISSN 1998-037X (Online)

CD-ROM ISSN 1998-0361

The New Iraqi Journal Of Medicine

The Official Journal Of The Iraqi Ministry Of Health

Volume 5 Number 2 August 2009

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journal published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer -review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list .The first tow issues of this journal appeared under the title of al Karkh journal of Medicine

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Indexed by Copernicus Index Journal Master List and EMR index medicus

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The histopathologic pattern of breast cancer in Iraq

Abstract

Background: Breast Cancer is the most frequent cancer in women worldwide .It is important to understand the histological pattern because histology as a prognostic factor has been well documented. No data is available about the histopathological cancer pattern of breast cancer in Iraq.

The aim of this paper is to report the histopathological cancer pattern of breast cancer in Iraq in the in the largest series of Iraqi patients with types of newly diagnosed cancers.

Patients and methods: In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004), 10277 cases of breast cancer, 464 males (4.5%), and 9813 females (95.5%) occurred in accounting for approximately 16 % of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Results: The histomorphological types seen among breast cancers indicated that there were 7876 cases (76.6%) with histology of Infiltrating duct carcinoma (IDC) not otherwise specified (NOS), which was found to be the most common type. This was followed in decreasing order by infiltrating lobular carcinoma in 562 cases (5.46 %); adenocarcinoma carcinoma in 558 cases (5.43%)

Conclusion: The histopathological cancer pattern of breast cancer in Iraq differs from the previously reported pattern in Asian and African countries such as India and Nigeria.

Keywords: Breast, Cancer, Iraq

Introduction

Breast Cancer is the most frequent cancer in women worldwide with 1.05 million new cases every year and represents over 20% of all malignancies among females [1]. Over 50% of breast cancer incidence occurs in the developed world. High-risk areas include Europe and North America. The lowest rates are reported from Africa and Asia. However, it still ranks as the commonest cancer among women in these regions. Incidence of breast cancer is increasing in most countries, including the areas, which have had previously low rates [2-4]. It is estimated that in 2001 there were approximately 80,000 new breast

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Patients and methods

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Results

In the present study, various morphological variants and patterns were observed. The histomorphological types seen among breast cancers indicated that there were 7876 cases (76.6%) with histology of Infiltrating duct carcinoma (IDC) not otherwise specified (NOS), which was found to be the most common type. This was followed in decreasing order by infiltrating lobular carcinoma in 562 cases (5.46 %); adenocarcinoma carcinoma in 558 cases (5.43%), epithelial 145 in cases (1.4%), medullary carcinoma 114 in cases (1.1%), Comedo carcinoma 67 (0.65%) (Table 1).

Discussion

Breast cancer incidence rates are increasing worldwide. In Iraq, it is the most common cancer accounting for 16% of all cancers in Iraqi patients. The continuing rise in breast cancer incidence has created an urgent need to develop strategies for prevention.

Few studies of international variation in breast cancer have considered tumor histology.

It is important to understand the relationship of histological type to etiology, and to allow separation of entities with distinct etiologies. Histology as a prognostic factor has been well documented. Patients with histology of Infiltrating duct carcinoma (IDC) (NOS) have a poor survival compared to other types [4, 5]. In the present study among the different histomorphological types, Infiltrating duct Carcinoma (NOS) was found to be the most common type occurring in cases (76.6%).

Histomorphological type	No. %
Infiltrating duct carcinoma.	7876(76.6%)
Infiltrating lobular carcinoma	562 (5.46%)
Adenocarcinoma	558 (5.43%)
Epithelial	145 (1.4%)
Medullary carcinoma	114 (1.1%)
Comedo carcinoma	67 (0.65%)
Phyllodes tumor	50 (0.48%)
Mixed ductal & lobular	48 (0.46%)
Infiltrating ductular	35 (0.34%)
Paget's disease	34 (0.33%)
Mucinous adenocarcinoma	24

Table 1: Distribution of cases according to histomorphological types

The histopathological cancer pattern of breast cancer in Iraq differs from the previously reported pattern in Asian and African countries such as India and Nigeria.

The commonest histological types of breast cancer in Nigerian women in a study conducted over a twelve-year period (January 1993-December 2004) were IDC (not otherwise specified) constituted the majority of breast cancer accounting for 75.5% while papillary carcinoma was the least common (2.7%). Ductal carcinoma in situ accounted for 6.6%.

In India the histomorphological types seen among 569 female breast cancers indicated that there were 502 cases (88.2%) with histology of IDC not otherwise specified (NOS), which was found to be the most common type. This was followed in decreasing order by infiltrating lobular carcinoma in 21 cases (3.7%); colloid carcinoma in 6 cases (1.1%), ductal carcinoma-in-situ in 6 cases (1.1%), metaplastic type in 5 cases (0.9%), schirrous carcinoma in 5 cases (0.9%), apocrine type in 4 cases (0.7%)

and the rest 20 cases (3.5%) with other types of carcinoma [7].

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